

Impact Study

Public Health & Therapeutics

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Context

Biodata resources have emerged as powerful tools in the fight against global health challenges. By providing researchers, healthcare professionals and policymakers with access to vast amounts of data, these platforms accelerate scientific discovery and enable more effective responses to public health crises. They also support discovery of new therapeutics through computationally-driven research efforts, in both academic and commercial contexts.

Biodata resources facilitate the integration of diverse data types, from genomics to clinical outcomes, allowing for a more comprehensive understanding of disease mechanisms and the development of innovative precision medicine strategies.

This series of case studies explores how biodata resources have assisted successes in the public and private sectors, speeding up the pace of research and enabling data-driven decision making.

Strengthening the global response to future pandemics

To tackle the COVID-19 pandemic, the [COVID-19 Data Portal](#), part of the [European COVID-19 Data Platform](#), was released in [April 2020](#). The COVID-19 Data Portal synchronised with COVID-19-related genomic, protein and microscopy data from the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), the Protein Data Bank in Europe (PDBe), UniProt, Electron Microscopy Data Bank (EMDB) and the Expression Atlas.

The number of researchers uploading sequence data soared in the months following the pandemic, with the Portal hosting over [8.9 million nucleotide sequences](#) as of September 2024 and [helping accelerate COVID-19 research](#). Usage of the COVID-19 Data Portal was significant during the pandemic, with about [11% of visits](#) (over 17,700 unique IP addresses) from pharmaceutical companies, national and regional health centres and government organisations. For example, the [COVID-19 Data Portal Poland](#) (a country-specific subset of the broader resource) enabled the country to [validate](#) the effectiveness of vaccination efforts by comparing vaccination rates to fatality rates in different administrative regions, as well as an exploration of factors that negatively affect patient outcomes (e.g. high levels of pollution).

The [BeYond-COVID \(BY-COVID\)](#) project, which builds upon the achievements of the COVID-19 Data Portal, has secured €12 million in funding from Horizon Europe. The project aims to offer extensive open data across various domains, including scientific, medical, public health, and policy, focusing on SARS-CoV-2 and other infectious diseases. In this context, BY-COVID directly funds [a range of open biodata resources](#) that contribute to the goal of making infectious disease data open and available for everyone, including [Pathogen Data Hubs](#) and the [COVID-19 Disease Map](#). Furthermore, as part of the BY-COVID initiative, the platform has now incorporated COVID-related data from the social sciences and humanities domain, sourced from the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA) ERIC. The platform is also being adapted to accept monkeypox viral data (monkeypox has been declared a [public health emergency of international concern](#)), demonstrating the COVID-19 Data Portal's potential to serve as a model for managing data related to other pathogens and diseases.

Collecting and sharing data to steward important ecosystems

EnteroBase is a genome database that captures data about bacterial pathogens, such as Salmonella, Streptococcus and Yersinia. It also provides [tools](#) to assemble, analyse and interpret bacterial genomes to provide insights for researchers and public health professionals. EnteroBase [is used](#) in public health reference laboratories around the world, including the UK, Ireland, France, Denmark, Canada, China and South Africa.

EnteroBase played a key role in efficiently investigating a Salmonella enterica serotype Poona outbreak among infants in France between August 2018 and February 2019. In particular, this biodata resource enabled two key approaches for the microbiological investigations:

- Phylogenetic analysis using two different techniques, including Single Nucleotide Polymorphism (SNP) analysis and core genome Multilocus Sequence Typing (cgMLST) analysis.
- Comparison of isolates from different outbreaks and time periods, whereby the French outbreak isolates were compared to isolates from the 2010-2011 S. Poona outbreak in Spain and S. Poona isolates from infants in Spain collected in 2018.

The comparison using cgMLST and SNP analyses confirmed that the 2010-2011 Spanish isolates were related to the French outbreak isolates, while the 2018 isolates were unrelated. EnteroBase provided an integrated platform to perform these genomic analyses, enabling the researchers to establish relationships between isolates from different countries and time periods. This was crucial for understanding the origins and persistence of the outbreak strain.

Investigations later revealed that the affected infants had consumed the same brand of rice-based powdered infant formula, leading to a recall for the formula manufactured at the identified facility. An urgent inquiry through the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control Epidemic Intelligence Information System for Food and Waterborne Diseases and Zoonoses identified two additional confirmed cases in Belgium and Luxembourg.

The Head of the French National Reference Centre has reaffirmed the importance of EnteroBase in combatting pathogen outbreaks, [stating](#), “During several investigations here in France, EnteroBase has allowed us to identify within minutes several outbreak-related cases in other European countries.”

New hope for cancer treatment

The [Protein Data Bank \(PDB\)](#) is a database for 3D structures of large molecules, such as proteins and nucleic acids. Between 2019 and 2023, data from the PDB facilitated the development of 34 new low molecular weight, protein-targeted agents approved by the US Food and Drug Administration for human use.

Examples of these include [Selinexor](#) (sold as [Nexpovio](#)), a drug used for adult patients with relapsed or refractory multiple myeloma, and [Sotorasib](#) (sold as Lumakras or Lumykras), which is used to treat adults with non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) when the cancer is advanced, and its cells have a particular genetic change.

For [Selinexor](#), the PDB contained structures of the XPO1 protein, which is involved in transporting molecules out of the cell nucleus. These structures helped researchers at the company Karyopharm understand how XPO1 works at an atomic level. They used computational tools to virtually dock and design small molecules that could bind to and block XPO1 activity, ultimately leading to the discovery of Selinexor. The PDB structures guided the optimisation of Selinexor to effectively inhibit XPO1 and realise its anti-cancer effects.

In the case of [Sotorasib](#), the PDB housed structures of the KRAS protein, which is commonly mutated in cancers. A specific KRAS mutation called G12C was known to drive tumour growth but was considered “undruggable” for many years. In 2013, researchers used PDB structures to design compounds that could irreversibly bind to G12C KRAS and inhibit its activity. Scientists at Amgen then used structure-guided drug design, relying heavily on PDB data, to discover and develop Sotorasib as an inhibitor of G12C KRAS. Co-crystal structures in the PDB revealed how Sotorasib bound to and inhibited the mutant protein, leading to a breakthrough in targeting this once elusive cancer driver.

Conclusions

Biodata resources have proven to be invaluable assets in addressing health challenges, and their impact can be felt at multiple levels, fostering innovation and enhancing health outcomes. From country-level insights to investigations specific to a location or disease, a broad range of databases can be leveraged by researchers, healthcare professionals and policymakers to accelerate scientific discoveries and drive more effective responses to public health crises.

Given the incalculable savings in both human lives and economic resources that can be achieved through preventing and tackling health issues, continued investment in comprehensive biodata resources is not just prudent, but essential for the future of global health and wellbeing.

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Appendix – Resources discussed

Resources	About
BeYond-COVID (BY-COVID)	BY-COVID is a database that provides comprehensive open data on SARS-CoV-2 and other infectious diseases for use in the scientific, public health and policy spheres. It builds on the One Health approach, a collaborative effort which recognises the connection between people, animals, plants and the environment, and ensures interoperability with other such databases.
COVID-19 Data Portal	The COVID-19 Data Portal, funded by EMBL-EBI, brings together relevant COVID-19 data sets and tools to accelerate scientific advancements during the pandemic. It is the primary entry point into the functions of the European COVID-19 Data Portal.
COVID-19 Disease Map	<p>The COVID-19 Disease Map is a repository of molecular mechanisms of SARS-CoV-2. It combines a large evidence base of literature with complex datasets to propose mechanistic models of SARS-CoV-2 infections and providing predictions for key targets of interventions.</p> <p>The COVID-19 Disease Map is open access, interoperable and community built.</p>
Electron Microscopy Data Bank (EMDB)	EMDB is a public repository of 3D electron microscopy maps and associated experimental data. It covers a variety of techniques, including single particle analysis, helical reconstructions and electron tomography and crystallography.
EnteroBase	EnteroBase is a large collection of data for analysis and visualising genomic variations within animal and human (enteric) bacteria. As of 2024, it contains a total of 1,190,836 bacterial strains. These include strains of Salmonella and Streptococcus, among others.

Resources	About
<p>European Nucleotide Archive</p>	<p>The European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) is a database that provides an extensive record of the worlds nucleotide sequencing information and covers elements like sequence assembly information, raw sequencing data and functional annotation. The site also provides a rich portfolio of services and tools to support the management of sequence data. The ENA is provided by EMBL-EBI, part of the European Molecular Biology Laboratory.</p>
<p>Expression Atlas</p>	<p>Expression Atlas is a public repository of gene and protein expression data across species and biological conditions, with the ability to visualise downstream analysis results, for researchers to explore co-expression.</p>
<p>Protein Data Bank</p>	<p>The Protein Data Bank (PDB) was established as the first open access digital data resource in all of biology and medicine. It is today a leading global resource for experimental data central to scientific discovery.</p> <p>Through an internet information portal and downloadable data archive, PDB provides access to 3D structure data for the molecules of life, found in all organisms on the planet.</p>
<p>Pathogen Data Hubs</p>	<p>The Pathogen Data Hubs are a set of tools, including workflows for data storage, sharing DNA sequence data and analysis, for a particular disease and/or geographic areas. Data Hubs exist for many infectious diseases, e.g. Ebola, Monkeypox, or for geographic regions or local areas, e.g. Kibera in Kenya.</p>
<p>UniProt</p>	<p>UniProt is the world's leading high-quality, comprehensive, and freely accessible resource of protein sequences and functional annotation, featuring the expert-curated core UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot. UniProt is mainly supported by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI), EMBL, and the US National Institutes of Health (NIH).</p>

Global Biodata Coalition

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The GBC acknowledges the work of [Research Consulting](#) in the preparation of these impact studies.

